

Mechanism of Shaving for Women - The Right Kind of Razor

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Abstract

Hair removal has been a primary practice amongst women since quite a few decades. These are a lot of techniques and methods that contradict theoretically and claim to be the best. As per the sample taken of 1000 women of different perceptions it was concluded that shaving has been the healthiest and easiest method of hair removal.

INTRODUCTION

Razor mechanics for usage for women

Hair removal has been a primary practice amongst women since quite a few decades. These are a lot of techniques and methods that contradict theoretically and claim to be the best. Shaving is one of the most popular techniques and has been practiced widely since 3000BCE.

Methods: In sixth century BCE, women used depilators, tweezers, pumice stones and sugar mixture similar as waxing.

Gillette created very first safety razor specially for women in 1914. This campaign was launched by Milady Decollete created by Gillette. Gillette gave an ad in

Harper's Bazaar in 1915 stating bare underarms were a necessity. By 1964, 98% of American women were shaving their legs.

Poor quality shaving blade can lead to inflammation of the skin. Recent data is used to provide brevity on qualities and features of different razors available in the market. Different razors and their biomechanical forces are discussed to conclude with the mechanics of the best razor available in the market.

Average hair growth rate of human hair is about 15 cm to 6 inches per year. Shaving is a process where highly sharpened metal edges are used to slice those continuously growing stubble.

Poor quality shaving can lead to significant lateral displacement, angular rotation and extensions of hair out of its follicle. There is a similar disturbance to the surrounding skin because of the softness of the epithelial tissue and hardness of the hair.

HAIR REMOVAL

Hair removal has been a very important aspect as far as beauty is concerned. Women want to look beautiful and they prefer habits like hair removal to add to their beauty and so that they are more beautiful than they would have naturally been. Basically hair removal is a healthy habit. It is said that hair removal; prevents from infections and bad odor. It also helps get rid of rashes and itchiness during summer. Hair removal was done basically for maintenance of personal hygiene. Personal hygiene has been mandatory since ages. It contributes to good health and keeps you in a fresh mood always.

HAIR REMOVAL TECHNIQUES

There are multiple techniques of hair removal such as

- 1) Waxing
- 2) Shaving
- 3) Tweezing
- 4) Scrubbing
- 5) Depilatory creams
- 6) Threading
- 7) Sugaring
- 8) Electrolysis
- 9) Laser

SHAVING

Shaving is the removal of hair, by using a razor or any other kind of bladed implement, to slice it down—to the level of the skin or otherwise. Shaving is most commonly practiced by women to remove their leg and underarm hair. Women sometimes also shave their chest hair, abdominal hair, pubic hair or any other bodily hair. Shaving is basically done using razors.

HAIR REMOVABLE INSTRUMENTS

Razor:

Razor is an instrument with a sharp blade or set of blades, used to remove unwanted hair from the face or body. **Razor** is also a bladed tool primarily used in the removal of unwanted body hair through the act of shaving. Kinds of razors include straight razor, disposable razor, and electric razors.

TYPES OF RAZORS

- 1) **STRAIGHT RAZOR** : A **straight razor** is a razor with a blade that can fold into its handle. They are also called **open razors** and **cut-throat razors**.
- 2) **DISPOSABLE RAZOR**: A disposable razor is a razor that can be used only once. After use it needs to be disposed. Disposable safety razors are highly similar in design to Cartridge Razors, constructed from inexpensive materials (commonly injection moulded polycarbonate), yet are meant to be wholly disposable after use with no blade sharpening or replacement possible. One device was invented in 1963 by American entertainer and inventor Paul Winchell.

3) **ELECTRIC RAZOR:** The electric razor (also known as the electric dry shaver) has a rotating or oscillating blade. The electric razor usually does not require the use of shaving cream, soap, or water.

NEED OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is about the fears of women in using Gillette Venus razor, the inhibitions of women before and after that is pre and post usage of the razor. All of these will be associated with purchase of women's razor.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- 1) To know the pre and post purchase perceptions
- 2) To study the women's personal hygiene habits and concerns on removal of their body hair in the age group of 16-40 years.
- 3) To know the fears and inhibitions of using hair removal instrument
- 4) To study the awareness of Gillette Venus Razor
- 5) To study the fears and inhibitions of women in using Gillette Venus Razor

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study is to study the personal hygiene habits and concerns of women regarding hair removal. Also to study how many women are aware of the existence of the product. Fears and inhibitions that women have regarding use of hair removal instrument and Gillette Venus Razor. We will also study pre and post purchase perception of Gillette Venus Razor.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research has been done on the basis of a questionnaire that was created keeping the parameters necessity, conscious, comfort, concern for hygiene, awareness, fears, inhibitions and different age groups of women in mind. Questionnaire had 27 questions which includes demographic data, personal hygiene, affordability, trust, fears and inhibition. The questionnaire was circulated to women of different age groups i.e. between the age of 16 to 40.

Problem statement: Razors engineered to be smooth on skin and healthy for hair.

LIMITATIONS

- 1) It was difficult to collect data of women who use razor or Gillette Venus Razor.
- 2) Few questionnaires were incomplete.
- 3) Not all women that were approached with questionnaire were ready to respond.

ABOUT RAZOR

Perret razor was invented in 1760s by a French barber named Jean Jacques Perret for the first time ever. It was L-shaped wooden guards that holds the razor and is suppose to reduce the damage done to the skin while shaving.

In 1880s, Meet King Camp Gillette invented a much safer razor for men. In 1915, first women razor was invented.

A different feminism embraced by some women in 1980s and 90s made it difficult to question the rules about beautiful appearance propagated by media moguls and enforced by less privileged men. One of the most iron-clad rules of being beautiful was, and is, shaving. It's no longer a secret that most women have bristling legs, arms, and armpits. The idea of hair removal was to achieve the smoothness of a baby's bottom which is impractical and destructive.

The Age, an Australian Publication shows an article written by Mimi Spencer, "What women doesn't abhor the eggy smell of depilatory cream, the searing pain of a blunt razor dragged up her shinbone, or the embarrassment of opening the door to the postman with crème bleach still clinging to her upper lip?"

Shockingly, women transition to shaving occurred without significance protest. It were only men who shaved before 1900s but around 1915 sleeveless dresses became popular opening up a whole new field of female , venerability for marketers to exploit. Gillette Razor Company by 1920 continues to cater to the shaving habits of both men and women today.

THE EVOLUTION OF RAZOR

In 1760, a French barber Jean Jacques Perret created the first straight razor for men which was used by some women. In 1844 the very first depilatory cream was created by Dr. Gouraud. It was named Poudre Subtile.

In 1915, Gillette created the first razor ever for women named Milady Decolletee. In 1907 an ad for X-Bazin Depilatory Powder began circulating, promising to remove "humiliating growth of

hair on the face, neck and arms.” A decade later, a leading women’s fashion magazine ran an ad featuring a woman with her arms raised and her armpits bare, the first of its kind.

Remington released the first electric women’s razor in 1940 after the success of a male version. Due to a war time shortage of nylon, more products and techniques for hair removal hit the market as women needed to go bar- legged more often.

Wax strips made their debut in the 1960s and quickly became the method of choice for removing unwanted hair under the arms or legs. The first laser-hair-removal tools hit the market in the mid-1960s, but soon fell out a favor due to their skin-damaging tendencies.

Although electrolysis had been around for nearly a century, it became more reliable and safe in the 1970s with the development of transistorized equipment. The decade also saw resurgences in the removal of bikini area hair as the swim suit fad of the 1960s stuck around.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HAIR REMOVAL AND THE CAVEMAN

Men were very resourceful at hair removal. They used to pull, scrape and pluck hair from bodies. They used sharpened rocks or flint blades to “scrape” hair off their faces and plucked facial hair with two sea shells held together. Reasons for hair removal in those times include benefits of having less mites on the body and keeping vicious animal away from having clew and handholds.

HAIR REMOVAL IN THE ANCIENT EGYPT

Ancient Egyptians may have revolutionized hair removal procedures. A very ritualistic culture overrun with conformity, hair removal may have been highly significant, making advanced to

hair removal methods important. Egyptians were master minds of bronze razors. Egyptians also used depilatory method called sugaring. It was applied on the skin and yanked off using strip of cloth which was pressed onto the paste. Because of extreme heat both men and women did it in Egypt on their heads.

HAIR REMOVAL AND MIDDLE EASTERNERS

No doubt borrowing the process for their Egyptian counterparts, Middle Easterners used the hair removal process of body sugaring that included sugar based paste. This paste was pulled off against the direction of hair growth. Bacterial growth was inhibited due to high sugar content. This method was born out of a bridal ritual. The night before marriage, Lebanese. Their heads. Removed by the bridal party. Brides maintained hairless body throughout her marriage to signify cleanliness and respect for husband.

EUROPIAN HAIR REMOVAL DURING THE MIDDLE AGES

In Middle age upper class women from Europe wanted to be pale. Plucked eyebrow was fashionable. During 15th century women plucked front to achieve a high forehead. Mothers of this time used outlandish hair removal poultices, bandages saturated with vinegar and cat's dung and even walnut oil to prevent hair growth on forehead. Depilating is a habit passed on by Greeks and Romans,

HAIR REMOVAL IN NORTH AMERICA

North Americans tweezed their whiskers between halves of clam shell, and circa 1700 American women apply poultices of caustic Ice to burn away. There is evidence of depilatories in United States by 1844. A new method was developed by physicians which involved inserting and

twisting a barbed needle with sulphuric acid into the hair follicle. Later it was changed and made as a new process called electrolysis.

HAIR REMOVAL IN SOUTH AMERICA

Rite of passage for Brazilian women was waxing. They used secretion from Coco de mono tree to remove hair.

HAIR REMOVAL IN MODERN TIMES

Smoothness was reinforced by the invention of the bikini in sixties. Most accepted methods of hair removal today are electrolysis and laser treatments.

MOST POPULAR HAIR REMOVAL METHODS

1) Abrasives or the friction method

Ancient Egyptians, Greeks and Romans are believed to have used stones like Pumice and the sharper volcano glass to remove hair.

2) Threading

Threading is popularly known as Khome in Arabic. It is a process in which hair is pulled from the roots using a looped thread. It is basically used to shape eyebrows. It is very popular in middle east and India and lasts up to 6 weeks.

3) Sugaring

It was introduced in ancient Egypt. It is a soft, sugar based paste which sticks only to hair not to the skin. It is a very popular and easy technique of hair removal.

4) Electrolysis

It is a process in which a thin metal needle gets to the base of the hair follicle and it is zapped with an electric current. This effectively cauterizes the hair follicle and prevents the growth of hair in future. This is an expensive and painful technique of hair removal. It also consumes a lot of time. Dr.Charles E.Mitchel practiced this method to remove ingrown eyelashes in the year 1875.

5) Laser

A laser light is a ray that targets the hair follicle as heat when it is cast onto the skin. This causes inflammation and the follicle permanently goes to the resting phase. It is not always advisable because it is expected to cause burns , skin discoloration and patchy regrowth of hair if the treatment was not performed properly.

6) Few Indian waxing method includes recipes like red lentils (masoor dal), sandalwood powder, orange peel powder and charoli (chironji) .

7) Few very popular methods are tweezing , bronze razor, bee wax and plucking.

8) Depilatory creams

These creams are used are applied on the skin and left for a while. It smoothens and softens the hair and later it is scrapped off. Depilatory creams in ancient days were made by using raisin,

pitch, white vinegar, powdered viper, ivy gum extracts, ass's fat ,she-goat's gall , bats blood and cat dung.

CONCLUSION

Razors have been used since ancient times but the purpose has remained same. The art of designing the right kind of blade has played a very important role in maintenance of hygiene. This study also concludes that razors can be the safest way to remove hair.

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